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PREDICTING FAILURE IN FIBRE COMPOSITES: LESSONS LEARNED FROM THE WORLD-WIDE FAILURE EXERCISE

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SUMMARY: The paper is aimed at providing an overview of some of the lessons learnt from the 'World-Wide Failure Exercise' (WWFE). This uniquely organised Exercise was launched by the authors to establish the status of currently available theoretical methods for predicting material failure in fibre reinforced polymer composites materials. The Exercise runs in two parts: Part A is devoted to providing full details of the theories together with predictions (made by their originators) for a common set of test cases, defined by the organisers. Part B focuses on a comparison of the theoretical predictions made in Part A against the experimental results (provided by the organisers), whilst allowing the participants to introduce improvements to their own theory, and to have a general 'right to reply'. In this paper, and in order to highlight some of the important conclusions obtained from the exercise, the theoretical predictions are compared with experimental data for a sub set of the test cases, chosen to illustrate certain gaps between the current predictive capabilities and test results. It will be shown that, even when analysing a simple laminate (which has been studied extensively over the last forty years) this can give rise to significant differences between the various theoretical predictions. Whilst some theories produce a good correlation with test results, thus providing increased confidence in the value of that theory as a design tool, others give an uncomfortably large deviation from the experimental observations, thereby shedding doubt on their usefulness as a design aid. For a fuller faith in design with composites, and among the key issues required for reducing the large discrepancy between test results and theoretical predictions are a proper handling of thermal residual stress, in-situ strength, matrix failure progression and large deformation behaviour.

KEYWORDS: failure, laminates, biaxial, stresses, strength.

INTRODUCTION

A co-ordinated study, known as the 'World-Wide Failure Exercise' (and abbreviated in this paper to WWFE), is currently being undertaken by the authors of this paper. It is aimed at providing a comprehensive description of the foremost failure theories for fibre reinforced plastic (FRP) laminates available at the present time, a comparison of their predictive capabilities directly with each other, and

a comparison of their predictive capabilities against experimental data. Selected workers in the area of fibre composite failure theories, including leading academics and developers of software/numerical codes, were invited to submit papers to a strictly controlled format. A series of laminate configurations, load cases and input data were clearly defined by the organisers. Test cases were selected to challenge the theories to the full, embodying a wide range of parameters. These included fibre type (carbon and glass), matrix type (different epoxies), lay-up configuration (unidirectional lamina and angle ply laminates, cross ply laminate, quasi-isotropic laminate and a generally oriented laminate) and loading conditions (which included uniaxial and biaxial situations).

A two-stage approach has been adopted for the exercise. Part A is devoted to providing full details of the theoretical models and failure criteria of the participants. Part B is concerned with comparing the theoretical results with experimental results. The arrangement allows both a 'blind test' of the predictive capabilities and a further opportunity for participants to offer refinements to the theories. Part A, has been completed, and published in a special edition of the journal 'Composite Science and Technology'. This contains :-

- the philosophy adopted for the 'exercise' [1].
- a full description of the test cases chosen [2].
- papers submitted by the contributors describing their theory and its application to the test problems [3-14].
- a direct comparison of the methodologies employed in each theory and the predictions made for each test case [15].

Part B is in the final stages of preparation. It too will be published in a special edition of the journal 'Composite Science and Technology' and will contain :-

- a full description of the experimental results for each of the test cases.
- a paper by each participant, drawing conclusions from the degree of correlation between experiment and their predictions.
- an overall comparison of the theories represented in the exercise against the experimental results.
- comments on the shortfalls in the theories and the experiments highlighted by the 'exercise'.
- recommendations for the next steps towards providing failure criteria with increased utility for the design community.

The authors are readily aware of the widespread interest in the composites community to see the results in this very contentious area, and of the general frustration at the length of time taken to complete the activity. The present paper has been written as part of the process for ensuring that the community is kept up to date with the lessons as they are emerging from the WWFE. As such, the paper should be treated very much as a 'late mid-term' 'work rather than the final, definitive, article. Thus a sub-set of the test cases has been selected to illustrate the gaps between certain of the current predictive capabilities and the experimental observations. Sources of the differences are discussed so as to provide a basis for future action towards closing the gaps.

DESCRIPTION OF THE FAILURE THEORIES

A major selection criterion for participation in the WWFE was that the failure theory being applied was distinctive and had originated within the group (see [1] for further details of the process). In the final event, eleven participating groups accepted the challenge and a total of fourteen theoretical approaches were employed, as shown in Table 1a. For the sake of simple identification and quick referencing, each

of the theories is referred to by the single name listed in the last column (it does not necessarily imply that the named person is the sole originator of the theory). It should be noted that Hart-Smith presented two complete papers, each containing a distinct theory. Sun and Chamis presented single papers, but each employed two different analytical models in order to tackle the full range of test cases (i.e. there were some limitations which prevented the use of any one model for all cases).

Table 1a A summary of the original participants and approaches represented in the exercise.

Contributor(s)/ Originators	Approach represented	Theory designation
1-Gotsis, Chamis et al	-ICAN	1-Chamis (1)
	-CODSTRAN (micromechanics)	2-Chamis (2)
2-Hart-Smith	Generalised Tresca theory.	3-Hart-Smith(1)
2-Hart-Smith	Maximum strain theory	4-Hart-Smith(2)
3-Eckold	British Standard pressure vessel design codes	5-Eckold
4-Edge	British Aerospace, In-house design method	6-Edge
5-McCartney	Physically based ‘Damage Mechanics’	7-McCartney
6-Puck and Schürmann	Physically based 3-D phenomenological model	8-Puck
7-Wolfe and Butalia	Maximum strain energy method	9-Wolfe
8-Sun and Tao	Linear analysis	10-Sun (L)
	Non-linear analysis (non-linear is FE based)	11-Sun(NL)
9-Zinoviev et al	Development of Maximum stress theory	12-Zinoviev
10-Tsai and Liu	Interactive progressive quadratic failure criterion	13-Tsai
11-Rotem	Interactive matrix and fibre failure theory	14-Rotem

One of the consequences of running an activity as international as the WWFE is that it takes a considerable length of time to complete. The participants are providing their contributions through goodwill, and within the constraint of their local priorities. Thus, despite the best efforts of the organisers, timescales do (and have) slipped. Part A was launched formally in 1994 and was published in 1998. Part B was launched formally in 1997 with an anticipated publication date in 2001. During the intervening period, progress in the development of new failure theories has continued. Indeed one of the problems faced by the organisers has been that some participants have been extending their theories and revising their contributions so regularly, that it has proved a challenge to extract a paper with sufficient stability to allow the refereeing process to be completed (thereby finalising Parts A and B) ! . Clearly, a major driver behind the WWFE is to act as a catalyst to initiate the development of new and improved failure theories. It has therefore been gratifying to see that process in action.

A further consequence of the long timeframe and the publicity associated with the WWFE, has been the emergence of further theories from new groups. This has proved to be something of a challenge for the organisers in trying to incorporate the recent participants whilst maintaining a level playing field with the original contributors. We believe that probity has been achieved, by releasing the required data packs in a judicious manner, in sequence with receipt of the Part A and B manuscripts.

A list of the new participants and the methods they are employing is shown in Table 1b. These papers are still under review and the outcome will be made available either within Part B or through a later

publication (a textbook, combining Parts A and B is anticipated).

Table 1b A summary of the new participants and approaches represented in the exercise.

Contributor(s)/ Originators	Approach represented	Theory designation
2-Hart-Smith	10% rule theory	15-Hart-Smith (3)
12-Cuntze	Failure Mode Concept	16-Cuntze
13-Bogetti et al	Maximum strain theory	17-Bogetti
14-Mayes and Hansen	Multi-continuum theory	18-Mayes
15-Huang	Bridging model	19-Huang

Full details of the characteristics of each theory can be found in the individual papers, and a summary in [14]. There are a few notable points which reflect Part A theories and new development made by some of the participants:-

- Eckold attempted to employ the philosophy embodied in the British Standards for FRP pressure vessels. Thus those predictions are intended to reflect safe design limits (ie for continuous service, environments etc), and **not failure**, thereby providing what would be expected to be a lower bound to the exercise, see Ref[4] for details.
- McCartney provided an approach based on damage mechanics. In Part A, predictions were given for only two test cases in the exercise. Further improvement was made in Part B to predict solutions for other test cases, see ref [8].

Six of the theories (Tsai, Edge, Wolfe, Rotem, McCartney and Eckold) presented in Part A were modified in Part B, in the light of making the experimental results available to the participants. The modifications resulted from perceived shortfalls in fidelity, where the originators could identify an improved methodology :-

- Tsai has provided a new method of dealing with the post initial failure analysis.
- Wolfe and Butalia submitted revised predictions of the majority of the test cases. They relaxed some of the empirically tuned parameters.
- Edge also modified some of failure criteria he used in Part A.
- Rotem attempted to consider the effects of matrix degradation on the stress strain curves.
- Eckold modified the cut-off in the stress strain curves.
- McCartney extended the transverse cracking model, originally applied to cross-ply laminates, to angle ply and quasi-isotropic laminates

In this paper the predictions of the modified theories will be distinguished from those presented in Part A. Wherever applicable, theories designated as Tsai-A, Wolfe-A, Edge-A, Rotem-A, Eckold-A and McCartney-A refer to Part A predictions whereas designated as Tsai-B, Wolfe-B, Edge-B, Rotem-B, Eckold-B and McCartney-B refer to the newly modified predictions.

DESCRIPTION OF TEST CASES AND THE CHALLENGES IMPOSED

The test cases were selected to challenge the theories to the full. The fourteen original test cases are

listed in Table 2, together with a fifteenth, which was provided to the participants in Part B.

Table 2 Details of the laminates and loading (test) cases

Test Case	Laminate lay-up	Material	Description of Required Prediction
1*	0°	E-glass/LY556	σ_y versus τ_{xy} envelope
2*	0°	T300/BSL914C	σ_x versus τ_{xy} envelope
3*	0°	E-glass/MY750	σ_y versus σ_x envelope
4*	(±30°/90°)	E-glass/LY556	σ_y versus σ_x envelope
5*	(±30°/90°)	E-glass/LY556	σ_x versus τ_{xy} envelope
6*	(0°/±45°/90°)	AS4/3501-6	σ_y versus σ_x envelope
7	(0°/±45°/90°)	AS4/3501-6	Stress-strain curves for $\sigma_y : \sigma_x = 1 : 0$
8	(0°/±45°/90°)	AS4/3501-6	Stress-strain curves for $\sigma_y : \sigma_x = 2 : 1$
9*	±55°	E-glass/MY750	σ_y versus σ_x envelope
10	±55°	E-glass/MY750	Stress-strain curves for $\sigma_y : \sigma_x = 1 : 0$
11	±55°	E-glass/MY750	Stress-strain curves for $\sigma_y : \sigma_x = 2 : 1$
12	(0°/90°)	E-glass/MY750	Stress-strain curves for $\sigma_y : \sigma_x = 0 : 1$
13	±45°	E-glass/MY750	Stress-strain curves for $\sigma_y : \sigma_x = 1 : 1$
14	±45°	E-glass/MY750	Stress-strain curves for $\sigma_y : \sigma_x = 1 : -1$
15**	±55°	E-glass/MY750	Deformed shape of a tube under pressure

* Biaxial failure stress envelopes under a wide range of biaxial stress ratios

** This Case was provided only in Part B whereas the rest was provided in Part A.

Some of the questions the Test Cases were set out to answer are listed in Table 3. They cover a wide spread of parameters ranging from a basic check on classical laminate theory prediction through to the more complex topics such as residual thermal stresses, in-situ strength, matrix failure progression, delamination, and large deformation.

Table 3: List of the major issues attempted in the exercise.

No	Issues to be solved	Test Case
1	Use of micro-mechanics for prediction properties/failure	1-14
2	Prediction of the biaxial failure of a lamina in isolation?	1-3
3	Prediction of various modes of failure?	4-14
4	Prediction of the whole laminates failure envelopes?	4-7
5	Thermal residual curing stress consideration?	1-14
6	In situ strength of an embedded lamina?	4-14
7	Matrix failure in tension, shear and compression?	4-14
8	Delamination and splitting?	4-14
9	Leakage of pressurised pipes?	4-6
10	Single material non-linearity?	4-14
11	Multiple material and structural non-linearities?	4-14

12	Thin and thick laminates?	6,9,14
13	Effects of lay up on strength and deformation?	4-14
14	Post failure modelling or degradation of composite?	4-14
15	Prediction of fibre failure?	4-7
16	Structural failure and specimen design?	6-8,15
17	Prediction of large deformation?	9,10,14

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Full details of the experimental results are described in Ref [3]. The experimental results originated from work carried out at UMIST (UK), DERA (UK), DVFLR (Germany), and Utah University (USA). The specimens for 50% of the Test Cases (No 3,9-14) were manufactured at DERA (UK). The specimens and test results for Test Cases No 6-8 originated from Utah University.

In most cases the results selected for any given set of loading cases were from tests carried out by the same investigators in the same laboratory. The experimental results were derived from tests on tubular specimens, except that for the Test Case 12 ($0^\circ/90^\circ$ laminate) where the results were obtained from coupons. The tubes were subjected to a combination of internal (or external) pressure, axial tension (or compression) and torsion. Each specimen was tested to failure at a fixed stress ratio in the test section. Unless otherwise stated the applied stresses were calculated based on initial (undeformed) tube dimensions with no allowance made for change of shape during loading. Most of the tubes tested were thin with a radius to thickness in the range of 30-50. However, in a number of instances, thicker tubes, with a radius to thickness down to 3, were tested in order to avoid instability and buckling occurrence. Full details of the unidirectional lamina properties and the experimental results and their origin can be found in refs [2,3].

Comparison of Theoretical Predictions and Experimental Results

In order to illustrate the predictive capabilities of the theories, a selection of Test Cases were chosen in the present work.

Test Case 4 : (±30°/90°), E-glass/ LY556 laminate, s_y versus s_x biaxial failure envelopes)

The complete biaxial failure envelopes are shown in Fig 1, together with the experimental results. The degree of correlation between the individual theories and the experimental results can be described as follows:

- All of the theories, except that of Eckold, predict that the biaxial strength in the tension-tension quadrant is larger than that under uniaxial loading alone.
- Hart-Smith's theories over-predicted and those of Rotem and Chamis (and to some extent that of Wolfe-A) under-predicted the biaxial strength of the laminate.
- Eckold's theory predicted the largest biaxial compressive strength (much larger than the observed values)
- The rest of the theories generally gave a closer correlation with the test data.
- The largest discrepancy between the experimental results and the theories occurred at a stress ratios of 2:1(Rotem) and near 1:-1 (Chamis). The difference between experiments and theories was around 8.
- The Part B modified theories, Fig 1(C), gave in general a much improved correlation with the measured data.

Fig 1 showing a comparison between the predictions of WWFE theories and Test Case 4. (a) and (b) based on Part A theories and (c) based on modified Part B theories.

Test Case 11 : ($\pm 55^\circ$), E-glass/ LY556 laminate, stress-strain response under a stress ratio ($S_y : S_x$) of 2/1

This laminate and loading configuration is used widely by industry and represents one of the largest markets for FRP materials, namely pipelines and pressure vessel applications. A key issue from the user perspective is to avoid any breach of containment (ie avoidance of leakage). Thus, the analysis of strength and deformation of this laminate should, among other challenges, give a sanity check on whether the current theories are capable of predicting leakage. Figure 2 depicts the ratio of the observed to the predicted failure stresses obtained from the original and modified theories.

Experimentally, the initial failure stress was taken as the point at which leakage was detected (see [3] for more detail). Assuming that a necessary condition for leakage is that the point of initial failure, as defined by a given theory, has been reached, then the results in figure 2a show that, all the theories employed in WWFE under-predict the initial stress. The lowest prediction (a factor of 6) was that of Chamis and the highest that of Wolfe-B. No theoretical predictions were offered by McCartney-A or Hart-Smith (1 and 2) for this aspect.

Experimentally, the final failure stress was taken as the point at which catastrophic (fibre) failure occurred (see [3] for more detail). The majority of the theories could handle this effectively, the exceptions being those of McCartney-A, Chamis (1), Rotem, Wolfe-A and Wolfe-B.

Fig 2. Bar charts showing the ratio of theoretical / experimental failure stresses for $\pm 55^\circ$ GRP laminate under SR = 2/1

Test Case 12 : (0°/90°, E-glass/ MY750 laminate, uniaxial stress-strain response)

This test case has formed the basis for many studies within the composites research community. Its attraction is that three distinct and sequential stages of failure take place (transverse cracking/matrix failure, longitudinal splitting and fibre tension) and the damage evolution process is clearly visible due to the translucent nature of the material (see [3] for more detail). It has further advantages in that the stress state within each lamina is (notionally) very simple to calculate.

The degree of correlation between each theory and experiment is depicted in Fig 3. The results are plotted in a normalised manner for each mode of failure.

Figure 3 Comparison between the WWFE theories and experiments for Test Case 12

The following points should be noted : -

- More than 75% of the theories were totally unable to predict the occurrence of the longitudinal splitting mode.
- All of the theories (except that of Eckold and McCartney) systematically under-estimated the initial failure strength (ie matrix failure), in some cases by 100%.
- The majority of the theories were able to capture, fairly accurately, the observed fibre tension failure.

DISCUSSION

The present paper has been written as part of the process for ensuring that the community is kept up to date with the lessons as they are emerging from the WWFE. A sub-set of the test cases has been presented to illustrate the gaps between certain of the current predictive capabilities and the experimental observations. Of course the other test cases, which are not shown here, are also crucial to the process. In particular, the ability of any given theory to predict the full complexities of the

stress/strain curves has proved to be of paramount importance in ranking the maturity of the theories.

Prediction of modes of failure:

The experimental results presented here have shown that various modes of failure were observed and these depend upon the lay-up and the loading conditions. It is therefore important that theories are able to capture these modes accurately.

a) **Fibre tension mode of failure:** This mode was encountered in a number of Test Cases. The

majority of the theories that did not employ a ply discount method (ie dropping the properties to zero after the occurrence of initial failure) were able to capture this mode and the correlation with the test data was promising.

- b) **Longitudinal splitting:** This was clearly observed in at least one Test Case (No 12). It is assumed to have occurred as a result of matrix tension failure in the adjacent plies. Hence, most of the theories that were successful in detecting matrix tension failure were able to capture its occurrence, albeit with various degrees of accuracy.
- c) **Matrix failure:** Various forms of matrix failure were encountered. For Test Cases 4-14, and on a lamina level, the matrix failure was a combination of one or more of the following: tension, compression or shear combined with fibre tension or compression.
- d) **Leaking:** For those Test Cases (e.g 9-11,13) where the specimens were in the form of tubes and where the loading was dominated by hoop tension, leakage under internal pressure was observed to take place. It occurred at a stress above that of initial failure (transverse matrix cracking) and below that of final failure (failure of lined specimens), albeit that depended upon the stress ratio and the lay-up. None of the theories employed was capable of predicting such mode of failure.
- e) **Structural instability:** Although the aim of the exercise was not directed at exploring the suitability of the WWFE theories to predict structural instability, the test results for some of the Test Cases (e.g.No 6) analysed exhibited failure of this type. Thicker specimens (tubes) were used occasionally to overcome this mode of failure (e.g in Case No 9). The use of thicker specimens resulted in a failure under tri-axial loads. None of the theories employed dealt with

structural response and the tri-axial failure of some of the Test Cases.

Ranking the WWFE theories:

Based upon the results of the selected Test Cases described briefly here and the rest of the Cases, a qualitative assessment is made on the confidence of the current theories to deal with a number of fundamental issues. Fig 4 shows the confidence level displayed by the WWFE theories against a number of parameters. It can be seen that the confidence level is very low for the prediction of leakage and multiple non-linearities, as none of the theories was capable of tackling these problems at all. On the other hand, a relatively high degree of confidence was shown by more than 50% of the theories when predicting fibre failure occurrence in a number of the Test Cases studied.

CONCLUSIONS

- The WWFE has served as a tool to pinpoint the current successes and gaps in the current understanding of predicting failure in composites.
- Running the WWFE in two stages has proven to be useful for ‘blind testing’ the current theories and for providing a further opportunity for the participants to offer refinements to their theory.
- The refinements made by five of the participants, are encouraging and likely to serve in advancing the science, thereby increasing the fidelity of predictive techniques.
- Fibre failure prediction is fairly mature among more than 50% of WWFE theories. In the remainder, differences between the measured and predicted final failure of more than a factor of 8 have occurred on occasions.
- Prediction of leakage in tubes under pressure was poorly tackled by the WWFE theories. As was highlighted earlier in this paper, all of the theories under-predicted the strength at which ‘initial failure’ occurred experimentally, as defined by leakage of fluid (Test Case 9,11,13) or matrix cracking (Test Cases 12,13). This may be attributed to the fact that the onset of initial failure for the tubular specimen may not be sufficient to produce leakage. Additional loading may be necessary in order to evolve a fully connected crack path through the tube wall from the inside to the outside. Clearly, there is still a need to develop the failure theories somewhat further in order to provide more accurate predictions of leakage failure stress.
- Although not evidenced by the sub-set of Test Cases chosen for this paper, other Cases within the WWFE have exhibited a highly non-linear stress/strain response. Such behaviour is entirely typical for the majority of polymer composite systems used today, which suggests that a truly generalised failure theory must contain the means to handle such behaviour, if accurate strength and stress-strain behaviour is to be predicted. All of the theories presented here are deficient to a greater or lesser extent in this area. The organisers believe that it is one of the major contributors to the substantial gap between the experiments and the 12 theories employed in predicting the deformation.
- Prediction of progressive failure behaviour is far from mature. Further illustration of this feature can be found in the upcoming special issue.
- Other major questions remain to be debated by the composites community:-
 - (a) How to deal with residual thermal stresses ?
 - (b) Should any allowance be made for in-situ lamina effects and, if so, how ?
- If this subject area were mature, one would expect to see a significant amount of unanimity between the predictions of each theory for a given Test Case. However, in general, the test cases have generated a fairly wide diversity in the predictions, with some extreme differences in evidence under certain circumstances. From a designer’s viewpoint this is less than ideal, and is reason enough for the composites community to build on the lessons emerging from the WWFE

- The readers are reminded to refer to the upcoming special issue of the journal ‘*Composites Science and Technology*’ that will contain all of the Part B papers and comprehensive conclusions.

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